

Event metadata

Event title	DOME - Machine Learning Best Practices & Recommendations
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	05/12/2024
Time of event	3pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>As the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) accelerates across life science research, the demand for standardised practices has become crucial to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and adherence to FAIR principles.</p> <p>In response to these needs, DOME (Data Optimization Model Evaluation) has been developed as a key solution - a set of community-wide recommendations designed to guide supervised ML analysis reporting in biological studies. DOME offers broad, field-agnostic guidelines to enhance the impact of ML applications while ensuring reproducibility. This framework not only supports robust model evaluation but also serves as a valuable resource for training and capacity building in life sciences.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/dome-ml
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Machine Learning http://edamontology.org/topic_3474
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for researchers, publishers, funders and policy makers who are committed to advancing best practices in machine learning.

Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	
Speakers	Dr Fotis Psomopoulos, Senior Researcher, Institute of Applied Biosciences (INAB), Center for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH)
Related material	None